

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF MATURITY TO FAMILY LIFE**Raximova Dilbar Muxitdinovna**

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Abstract: A new epoch Uzbekistan is entering the third renaissance period, thanks to the wise policy of the President, care for the rise of our youth in the Republic has officially taken place among the issues of state importance. A number of scientific researches about family relations have been conducted and are being conducted in Uzbekistan. Scientists mainly worked in the direction of national characteristics of the family. The issue of socio-psychological factors of maturity to family life is at the centre of our focus as a scientific problem today. In particular, the sharp increase in the number of rulings in recent years calls for increased attention to family issues.

Keywords: activity, profession, self-determination, self-expression, social status, individual, matrimonial maturity.

Introduction**Discussion**

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev: "You know well that the slogan "We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people" is spreading widely and entering our lives more and more deeply. But who will take on the responsible task of creating such a bright and prosperous future for Uzbekistan?"

Of course, only you, our dear young people, who have mastered modern knowledge and skills, think independently, and always live with a sense of belonging to the fate of the country, are able to boldly go out into the field and solve the tasks that life itself sets before us today" [1] is very important for all of us.

The growth and development of society is in the hands of the growing young generation. In addition to mastering science and learning science, acquiring a profession in the educational system, now they are beginning to feel the desire to plan their personal lives and build a family. By this time, young people begin to have different views on family relations. It is necessary to form young people mentally and spiritually, to be able to properly influence their psyche. It is one of the urgent problems of the present time to make young people mature enough for family life, not to stumble in starting a family, but to have enough imagination and to prevent deformations in the family.

The importance of imparting scientific knowledge about family life to young people is that it is necessary to form social-psychological ideas about family relations, to inculcate in them the need to have a profession in order to build a full-fledged happy family. It is particular importance in our research to prepare them for family life by forming their perceptions of the factors of marriage and the main functions of the family for matrimonial maturity. It is worth noting that adolescents are biologically mature for family life, but also psychologically mature, which guarantees the possibility of building a happy family in the future. Because the strength of the society depend on the strength of the family.

Maturity for family life is formed differently in each person. A person's level of education, as well as family conditions, are factors that shape social and psychological perceptions. We mainly used the scientific, philosophical and psychological views of Eastern thinkers in the process of studying this issue. We referred to the works of Eastern scholars Abu Nasr Farabi, Yusuf Hos Hajib, Avicenna, Amir Temur, Alisher Navai and others.

Methods and materials

Farabi's views on human perfection, happiness, morals, attitude to religion, philosophical concepts, teachings enriched the moral theory. We can draw our own conclusions from these thoughts. That is, the thoughts that real happiness can only exist when one's kindness to others, oppression disappears, family members' sincere relations with each other, and their affection for each other constitute the happiness of people in this family, in addition, each parent is the primary teacher and a guide for their children who makes the conclusion about the condition of the child [3].

Elucidating various aspects of family relations, Avicenna, first of all, set a number of requirements for the head of the family. As the head of the family, he should acquire both theoretical and practical aspects in the family. If the leader of the family is uneducated, he will not be able to educate his members, and consequently, he will not be able to achieve positive results. Bad upbringing can have a bad impact not only on this family, but also on neighbors and the neighborhood.

Avicenna believes that raising a child in a family is the primary duty of parents, regardless of their position in society. Whether a parent is a head of state or a citizen, he is responsible for the child's education. Heads of state and leaders should set an example for everyone in terms of child education. If Avicenna's requirements for child education, psychology of education, and leaders were very relevant at that time, they have not lost their power even

today. This work is covered in detail in the section "Politics of the brave and child's work", i.e. "Father's attitude towards child education". In his opinion, education, i.e. parents, hired person "must influence the child's soul not only with words, but also in practice. /Avicenna. Tadbiri Manzil, page 44/.

Thoughts of Avicenna on love and marital relations are also noteworthy. "The highest love," he says, "is human love, and this kind of love makes a person generous, makes him kind-hearted and attractive." According to scientist, love imposes a lot of moral and legal responsibility on a person. When he says that the basis of human happiness is not love, he understands being in love. He emphasizes marriage with love as the basis of family strength. Avicenna's thoughts on labor education are also noteworthy. Every child, he says, must be taught some kind of occupation. If a young man learns a trade, is able to apply it in life and provides for the family thanks to his independent trade, his father considers it necessary to marry him off. So, this is the scholar's opinion about the age of social and economic maturity necessary for starting a family, and it will never lose its importance. /G'.B.Shoumarov "Family psychology" - T. "Sharq" 2013. pages 18-21/

Based on this, the great scientist's thoughts on medicine, human education, and family relations are very valuable, and they will be a worthy contribution to the development of social sciences and the ethics of human relations at that time. social psychological significance.

Yusuf Khajib, among many great scientists of Central Asia, made a great contribution to the culture and development of the peoples of the Muslim East. According to the poet, having a child and raising it is a great happiness for every person, without them life has no meaning. But this thing imposes a lot of responsibility on parents, which is both a duty and a debt for every parent to be able to cope with it. That is why Yusuf Khos Khajib considered family education to be the basis of a child's moral development.

Yusuf Khos Khajib praises the love between people. He believed that love is the guarantee of family happiness and social success. Before getting married, a young man should know the identity of the bride, her origin, age, character and behavior, he says. / G. B. Shoumarov "Family psychology" - T. "Sharq" 2013.20 pages/.

Unsurmaoli Kaikovus is a scientist who made a worthy contribution to the philosophy and pedagogy-psychology of Central Asia and the East in general. At the age of 63, he wrote "Nightmare" to his son, in which he describes his issues of child upbringing, family life, and personal development.

It is known that "Qabusnoma" is considered one of the rare works on education that it is considered among the works of the famous Indian masala "Kalila and Dimna", "Siyosatnoma" by Nizamulmulk, and "Saodatnoma" by Nasir Khisrav. The ideas and instructions contained in it are an important program for parents, especially in raising teenagers and young adults. . / G. B. Shoumarov "Family psychology" - T. "Sharq" 2013.21 pages/.

Unsurmaoli Kaikovus's instructive thoughts about the need to learn and learn about the factors that influence a child's maturity and personality maturity, presented in Qabusnoma, serve as a spiritual heritage for us.

Sohibkiran Amir Temur's instructive, vital advices and meaningful teachings are of particular importance due to their breadth of content and meaning, strength of logic, influence, and being built on the basis of universal values, they are an immense treasure, morals. we can say programs.

A business man, possessor of courage and enthusiasm, resolute, enterprising and alert person is better than thousands of idle and indifferent people.

Although the conclusion of the case is hidden behind the veil of fate, it is necessary to ask for advice from sane and alert people and to know their opinions.

I became aware of the condition of the population, I saw the elders in the ranks of the elders, and the younger ones in the place of children.

Concerned about getting my sons, grandsons and relatives married, I paid attention to choosing a bride. I considered this work equal to state work. I inquired about the genealogy of becoming a bride. Through special people, I determined his health and physical maturity. If the bride-to-be is free from all defects with her pedigree, morals, health and strength, I gave a wedding spectacle to the country and gave her a bride.

I forbade my sons, grandsons and relatives to drink even a drop of wine and approach their wives. Because a child born under the influence of wine will affect the corruption of the genealogy, so I took this pure path.

I had a conversation with the scholars and asked for people with pure intentions and pure hearts. [Ibrahim Iskandarov: Anthology of Uzbek pedagogy. Tashkent "Teacher" publishing house, 1995, pp. 230-238.

Alisher Navoi states that a decent person is the best of all people, he is more beautiful than the high-ranking people and more respectable than the rich people. In his opinion, the beautiful opens the heart, hides the ugly life, the beautiful with good behavior is a paradise, and the bad-natured Ugly is a hellish

giant. Navoi highly appreciates beauty and fine art and emphasizes that fine art is the key to the spiritual world and perfection of man. /E. Umarov, R, Karimov, M. Mirsaidova, G. Aykho'jayeva "Basics of Aesthetics" publishing house named after Cholpon. Tashkent-2010. Pages 24-26/.

The place and importance of our great grandfather Alisher Navoi, who has unique irrevocable ideas about life culture, manners, and love, is priceless not only for the peoples of the East, but also for advanced development factors. His work "Mahbub-ul-Qulub" is a large treatise devoted to the problems of everyday life, manners, and education of the great scholar. In this work, Navoi describes the achievements he saw and knew throughout his life, the lifestyle, character, and spiritual life of ordinary people and the observations he has collected on their customs, good and bad qualities.

It is not for nothing that the work is called "Mahbub-ul-Qulub" or "love of hearts". Because in this work, Navoi describes the most necessary lessons for people and focuses on the development of good qualities that allow them to get out of various events and situations in marriage and family life. expresses great thoughts about family relationships. In it, he mentions how beautiful, natural and necessary for human development there are three types of love that exist in the human world. "Human love, true love glorifies the ideals of two sexes achieving perfection in marriage. This rare work is very valuable even for our time. Navoi stops at the place of a woman as follows: "A good wife is the state and happiness of the family. Her cleanliness, the calmness and tranquility of the owner of the house are from her, if she is cheerful - she is happy, if she is polite - she is happy." is. If he is smart, there will be order in the household, tools will be in order. If a person meets such an honest couple, if he achieves such happiness, he will have a confidant in sorrows and difficulties, and a close friend in open and secret pains. Sympathy is what happens to you in marriage. He is your helper when every calamity comes from the upside-down sky. If sadness comes to the heart, it is a companion, if weakness and illness come to the body, then its soul also perishes. must be. . / G. B. Shoumarov "Family psychology" - T. "Sharq" 2013.22 pages/.

Conclusion

In the East, serious importance has been attached to the preparation of young people for family life since ancient times. They have come down to us in the form of "Admonition", "Pandnoma", "Wisdom". In these sources, in preparing young people for life, first of all, human qualities should be formed in them, the family is sacred, and it is a program for today's youth. serves as an action.

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Our brief analysis above shows that among Eastern thinkers there are a lot of scientists who are interested in family problems and have left their valuable thoughts in this regard for future generations. indicates that the appearance is not repeated.

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